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TRANSFORMATION OF HOLIDAY CULTURE UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF THE REVOLUTION OF DIGNITY

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The purpose of the article is to characterise the development of modern holiday culture under the influence of the Revolution of Dignity and to study its impact on modern cultural processes in Ukraine. Holiday culture unites various historical and cultural stages of Ukrainian society. At the same time, at the present stage of development, holidays acquire new expressive and symbolic forms, unite citizens with common ideas, and create the spiritual core that unites us into a conscious nation. The research methodology involves the use of general scientific, historical, comparative, analytical, and axiomatic methods for a systematic analysis of the impact of the Revolution of Dignity on the holiday culture of Ukraine in the 21st century. The scientific novelty lies in the fact that the article outlines general trends in the development of the Ukrainian holiday calendar after the Revolution of Dignity and in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war since today's social challenges affect changes in the new holiday calendar of Ukrainians. Conclusions. The article provides an analysis of the development of modern holiday culture under the influence of the Revolution of Dignity and its impact on modern cultural processes in Ukraine. The transformation of traditional and familiar holidays is revealed. On the examples of the introduction of public holidays and anniversaries, the relationship between the main events of public life and the country's holiday calendar is demonstrated. It is proved that Ukrainian holiday culture, as a phenomenon of the Ukrainian people, has an active influence on the development and formation of the national identity of both the younger generation and the adult population of the country. Thus, the uniqueness of the spiritual richness of the Ukrainian holiday makes it an invaluable pedagogical asset for educating young people, preserving national traditions for future generations.

Keywords: holiday; holiday culture; Revolution of Dignity; public holiday; commemorative day; calendar of public holidays

Introduction

The phenomenon of holiday culture is a kind of dialogue between history and modern times, and is an integral genetic component of the Ukrainian people. Holiday culture unites various historical and cultural stages of life of the Ukrainian society, and at the same time, at the present stage of development, holidays acquire new expressive and symbolic forms. Usually, holidays change under the influence of various social events and reflect the feelings and moods of the present. It is the social challenges of our time that are influencing the changes in the new holiday calendar of Ukrainians. The Revolution of Dignity and the subsequent military aggression of the Russian Federation significantly affected the social, economic and political processes in our state, and accordingly, there were changes in the holiday calendar of Ukraine.

Recent research and publications analysis. Research of modern Ukrainian holidays in the cultural and scientific direction is reflected in the works of such authors as Z. Boryk (2015) "Intangible cultural heritage of Ukraine in the context of social and cultural development policy of the state", I. Petrova (2019) "Cultural and leisure practices in the system of public administration", T. Haievska (2006) "Folk rites in independent Ukraine", K. Haidukevych, (2016) "The specific nature of the organisation of mass sports and art events", O. Kis (2018) "Stolen holiday: historical transformations of the meaning of the International Women's Day (8 March)", O. Limanska (2008) "Calendar holiday as a component of Ukrainian ritual culture (on the material of Slobozhanshchyna)", V. Pohrebnoi, (2013) "A holiday in a man's life". However, they all relate to the development of Ukrainian mass holidays before the Revolution of Dignity. Modern political and social changes have significantly affected the development and formation of the Ukrainian holiday calendar, the challenge ahead is to rethink the traditional holiday culture of Ukrainians and consider innovative changes in Ukrainian calendar holidays that have influenced the development of modern Ukrainian culture.

Purpose of the article

The purpose of the article is to characterise the development of modern holiday culture under the influence of the Revolution of Dignity and to study its impact on modern cultural processes in Ukraine. Research methods. The author of the article applies the general scientific method, and provides a systematic analysis of the influence of the Revolution of Dignity on the Ukrainian holiday culture of the 21st century using the comparative and axiomatic method. The scientific novelty lies in the fact that the article outlines general trends in the development of the Ukrainian holiday calendar after the Revolution of Dignity and in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war.

Main research material

The holiday is an integral part of the modern cultural process and is a multifaceted and socio-cultural phenomenon that reflects the life moments of both individuals and society as a whole. Holiday culture has its own historical, social and cultural

sources, reflects a rich national cultural heritage that goes back deep into the past. Holiday culture influences the development and formation of the human worldview, reproduces the historical, moral, ethical and cultural values of the people, and is an integral part of human existence.

Ukraine is a country with a multinational population. This feature determines an extremely rich variety of regional traditions (political, cultural, religious, linguistic, etc.). Accordingly, there is diversity and pluralism in the area of celebration. O. Kurochkin (2014), who studied the features of modern holiday culture, drew attention to the ideological eclecticism of the official holiday calendar of our country, which reflects memorable dates and events of various content and origin. On the basis of the careful analysis, it could be said that there are secular and religious, national and international, political and cultural, rural and urban traditions. It is known that the calendar has church holidays (mainly Orthodox) — Christmas, Easter, Trinity, etc.; holidays of the Soviet calendar — Labour Day, International Women's day; holidays of Ukrainian statehood — Constitution Day, Independence Day, Ukraine's Unity Day, etc.), as if the country today lives in several time dimensions. "Such a heterogeneous picture is already at the highest official level of the national holiday system. In everyday life, taking into account the ethnic, confessional, political, professional, age-related, and now a socio-economic mosaic of Ukrainian society, the real situation is much more complicated" (Kurochkin, 2014, p. 7).

The events of the Revolution of Dignity in 2013-2014 became a turning point in the history of our state. Thus, Russian military aggression, the occupation of part of Ukrainian territories and military battles in eastern Ukraine affected the rise of national culture, which led to certain changes in the Ukrainian holiday calendar. As a result of recent events, it has been replenished with new Ukrainian holidays. One of the first was the Day of Dignity and Freedom celebrated on 21 November. The proclamation of this holiday was intended to promote the establishment of the ideals of freedom and democracy in Ukraine, preserve the memory of the fateful events in Kyiv and Ukraine at the beginning of the 21st century, and convey true information to future generations. This day is a tribute to the patriotism and courage of citizens who stood up for democratic values, human rights and freedoms, the European choice of our country in autumn 2004 and in November 2013 – February 2014, and the national interests of our state (President of Ukraine, 2014b).

The Day of Heroes of the Heavenly Hundred commemorates the tragic events of 20 February 2014, when during the Revolution of Dignity, on Instytutska Street in Kyiv, human blood was shed and were numerous victims. The shooting of protesters, the storming of a tent city, up to a hundred innocent victims were followed by the collapse of the Yanukovych regime. The Heavenly Hundred has become a symbol of dignity and freedom. This memorable day was set by the decree of the President of Ukraine Petro Poroshenko on 11 February 2015 in honour of the great civic and national courage, strength of mind of citizens who gave their lives during the Revolution of Dignity, defending human rights and freedoms, the ideals of democracy, thanks to whom "the course of the history of our state has changed" (President of Ukraine, 2015b). The words heroism, sacrifice, patriotism became consonant with the heroes of the Heavenly Hundred. For modern Ukrainians, their heroic deed has become an integral part of our history. The right to live in a civilian society, freedom of expression, and aspirations for

freedom have become an integral part of the lives of millions of our citizens. The Revolution of Dignity and subsequent events of the hybrid war on the part of the Russian Federation led to the development of the national movement, and the first volunteer military units were created. Therefore, on 14 March, we celebrate the Day of the Ukrainian Volunteer. The holiday was founded in order to further strengthen the patriotic spirit of citizens, honour the participants of volunteer groups and draw public attention to caring for them, and support public initiatives (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2017).

The Day of Defenders of Ukraine, which is a national holiday, was also established by the Presidential decree (President of Ukraine, 2014c) on the 14th of October in 2014, a year later, in 2015, it became nationwide. On 14 July 2021, the Verkhovna Rada renamed the holiday the Day of Defenders and Defendresses of Ukraine. The 14th of October combines three festive events, namely: the religious holiday of The Intercession of the Theotokos, Ukrainian Cossacks' Day, and the Day of the Creation of the Ukrainian Insurgent Army. Thus, it becomes clear that the glorious Cossack past is combined with the heroic present. For most Ukrainians, Defenders Day is perceived as part of our historical past, so with the beginning of the war against the Russian invaders, the Feast of the Intercession is perceived organically and meets the needs of society. Since 2015, the holiday is celebrated at the state level. According to the fifth President of Ukraine Petro Poroshenko: "The 14th of October, the intercession of the Most Holy Theotokos, has been a holiday of defenders of the native land since Cossack times. Therefore, last year, deliberately deleting from the Ukrainian calendar someone else's, artificially introduced holiday of the Russian occupying army, I chose the 14th of October" (Horova, 2015). The courage of our soldiers and officers, heroism, self-sacrifice have become integral symbols of the Ukrainian soldier.

Military holidays have become an integral part of the Ukrainian calendar. The Presidential Decree of 22 November 2018 established the Day of Foreign Intelligence, which is celebrated on 24 January. The introduction of the holiday is caused by the significant contribution of intelligence officers to protecting the country's national interests from external threats, strengthening the state's defence capability, as well as "starting modern traditions of honouring the achievements of Ukraine's foreign intelligence" (President of Ukraine, 2018). The prerequisites of the holiday have historical roots, in 1919 when the first national intelligence unit appeared in the Ukrainian army. It was created as part of the Political Department of the Directory of the Ukrainian People's Republic (UPR). Thus, on the 24th of January, the foreign information department started its work, the main idea of which was intelligence and counterintelligence against existing enemies of the UPR, as well as against countries - potential adversaries. Therefore, this is an important date, which refers us to our history and the struggle for our statehood.

The events of the Revolution of Dignity and Russian aggression in the East of our country led to the restoration of the National Guard. Modern units of the National Guard of Ukraine were created on 12 March 2014 by the law of Ukraine "On the National Guard of Ukraine". On the basis of the internal troops of Ukraine, volunteers who stood up for the defence and integrity of their state. In accordance with the Presidential Decree of 18 March 2015, we celebrate the day of the National Guard of Ukraine on 26 March (President of Ukraine, 2015a).

Also on 29 July, Ukraine marks the Special Operation Forces (SOF) Day, which was established by the Presidential Decree of 26 July 2016. This holiday was established to

confirm the high appreciation by the state leadership of the role of the Special Operations Forces of the Armed Forces of Ukraine in ensuring the state's defence capabilities and to promote the further development of national military traditions. "The Special Operation Forces consist of special units and information and psychological special operations units" (President of Ukraine, 2016). The Special Operation Forces personnel are an elite branch of the armed forces: motivated professional military personnel with high training. They are able to organise and conduct subversive and guerrilla activities behind enemy lines, and free hostages. The main motto of the Special Operations Forces of the Armed Forces of Ukraine is the battle slogan of Svyatoslav the Brave — "I Come at You!".

The Infantry Day is a modern military-professional holiday, celebrated on 6 May. It is related to the events of 1648 when the Cossacks won the battle near Zhovti Vody (Yellow Waters) under the leadership of Bohdan Khmelnytsky. The event of 6 May 1920, was no less important for the Ukrainian army. It was the time when the First Winter Campaign of the UPR Army ended. The holiday is established by the decree of the President of Ukraine dated 19 April 2019. Its purpose is to honour the courage and heroism of the soldiers of the Land Forces of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, shown in the struggle for freedom, independence and territorial integrity of Ukraine (President of Ukraine, 2019). During the active phase of hostilities in the Russian-Ukrainian war, on the 6th of May, Chief of Staff of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, Lieutenant-General Serhii Shaptala, noted that the infantry is a great and serious force in a difficult war for independence, freedom, justice and the future, so Ukrainians respect the infantry. He thanked all the infantrymen who defend the freedom of Ukraine in fierce battles and protect the entire civilized world. He stressed that he is an infantryman and is proud of it ("Den pikhoty — tse sviato", 2022).

A memorable date is the 13th of June, 2014. Mariupol, a major port and industrial centre (7% of the country's total industrial output), was liberated by Ukrainian armed forces. This became a turning point in the war in eastern Ukraine (Donetsk Regional state Administration, 2018). For the first time, the holiday was solemnly celebrated at the state level in 2016, on the second anniversary. In 2021, a military parade was held during the solemn events. According to military journalists, "for the seventh year in a row, this is a significant day not only for the residents of Mariupol, but also for the whole Ukraine" ("Sviato svobody ta mohutnosti", 2021).

On the 5th of July, 2014, the cities of Sloviansk and Kramatorsk, which had been occupied by Russian special forces for almost three months, were liberated from pro-Russian militants. This event was the reason to mark a memorable date in the Ukrainian calendar. During the military operation, in July 2014, Ukrainian military units liberated Kostiantynivka, Druzhkivka, Bakhmut from Russian militants. In the liberated cities, the life gradually returned to normal, municipal and social services began their work. "Since then, every year on the 5th of July, local residents of the liberated cities, and the whole of Ukraine, celebrate the day when the Ukrainian military saved Slavyansk and Kramatorsk from terrorists. There is a festive procession in embroidered shirts, with blue and yellow flags, as well as music concerts" (Mosondz, 2021).

In Ukraine, the volunteer movement began in the 90s, and it was officially recognised on 10 December 2003 by a resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers. The Revolution of Dignity, the events of 2014, namely the military aggression in eastern Ukraine,

caused a massive surge in the volunteer movement to support the Armed Forces of Ukraine and Ukrainian volunteers. Volunteers bore a huge burden in the war with the Russian occupier in eastern Ukraine. “The modern history of the struggle for Ukraine’s independence proves to everyone that volunteering is one hundred percent the vocation, the desire of a sincere and highly spiritual person to make the world a better place, to help everyone who needs protection and support” (“Ukraina ta svit”, 2017). Although the Volunteer Day, established back in 1985 on the initiative of the UN General Assembly, is an international celebration, it is widely celebrated in modern Ukraine since 2014.

The Day of Crimean Tatar’s struggle for their rights is a memorial day in Ukraine, celebrated annually on 18 May, the anniversary of the deportation of the Crimean Tatar people in 1944. The Day of Crimean Tatar’s struggle for their rights was established to support the struggle of Ukrainian citizens — Crimean Tatars for their rights as an indigenous people in the temporarily occupied Crimea. 70 years after the deportation by the Soviet regime, the Crimean Tatars in the conditions of occupation of Crimea again faced the threat of discrimination on their native land (President of Ukraine, 2014a).

Summing up the development of the Ukrainian holiday calendar, it can be noted that the events of the Revolution of Dignity and military aggression brought to the calendar many military holidays, professional holidays tied to various military units, memorable dates related to hostilities in the east of our state. For example: Day of Foreign Intelligence of Ukraine, Day of the National Guard of Ukraine, Infantry Day, Day of Liberation of Mariupol from Russian invaders, Day of Liberation of the cities of Slavyansk and Kramatorsk from pro-Russian terrorists, Day of Special Operations Forces of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, Day of Remembrance and Reconciliation, Day of the National Police of Ukraine, Dignity and Freedom Day.

Existing traditional holidays of Ukrainians have acquired a new patriotic content, for example: Day of the National Flag, Day of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, Day of the Ukrainian Cossacks, The Intercession of the Theotokos, Embroidery Day, International Mother Language Day, Day of Ukrainian Writing and Language — have been celebrated in a new format, and acquired a completely different meaning. Ukrainians have begun to rethink and understand Ukrainian state symbols and public holidays in a new way. Special attention should be paid, for example, to the celebration of the Day of the National Flag. Previously, Ukrainian citizens perceived it in the context of celebrating Independence Day, but the rethinking of our symbol was only after the Revolution of Dignity and subsequent events. It is significant that young people are actively involved in the promotion of modern Ukrainian holiday culture, through social networks they organise flash mobs and events in support of the Ukrainian army, all-Ukrainian values, and ideals. T. Hrančak (2017), DSc in social communications, PhD in history, argues that festive culture fosters patriotism among the younger generation, and “the rise of the state and patriotism calls for the unity of the people in the face of modern threats and challenges” (p. 320).

Modern Ukrainian researcher of festive culture N. Stishova (2017) considers that the main function of the holiday is to unite society, foster a tolerant attitude towards people of any race or religion. The introduced new holidays clearly serve to unite the citizens of Ukraine. At the same time, in order to preserve one’s identity, it is necessary to preserve ancient traditions, so “professional ethnographers, folklorists, and cultural

workers try to recreate the festive ritual culture using the method of purposeful reconstruction of calendar customs” (p. 183).

Holidays recreate folk customs and rituals, reflect the Ukrainian mentality and worldview, consolidate and unite Ukrainians around common interests both abroad and in their country. They unite citizens with common ideas, create the spiritual core that unites us in a conscious nation.

Conclusions

The article provides an analysis of the development of modern holiday culture under the influence of the Revolution of Dignity and its impact on modern cultural processes in Ukraine. The transformation of traditional and familiar holidays is revealed. On the examples of the introduction of public holidays and anniversaries, the relationship between the main events of public life and the country’s holiday calendar is demonstrated. New holidays have been added to the state calendar of public holidays, mainly of a military nature or related to the events of 2014, which is fully consistent with the process of decommunisation of society.

It is proved that Ukrainian holiday culture, as a phenomenon of the Ukrainian people, has an active influence on the development and formation of the national identity of both the younger generation and the adult population of the country.

The specific nature of Ukrainian holiday culture has a multicoloured palette, and its uniqueness encourages Ukrainians to preserve and multiply the treasure of the national ethnic group. Thus, the uniqueness of the spiritual richness of the Ukrainian holiday makes it an invaluable pedagogical asset for educating young people, preserving national traditions for future generations. Ukrainian holidays are a cultural fund of national traditions, rituals, and beliefs, which originally regulated not only the leisure time of Ukrainians, but also influenced the social and everyday aspects of people’s lives.

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ТРАНСФОРМАЦІЯ СВЯТКОВОЇ КУЛЬТУРИ ПІД ВПЛИВОМ РЕВОЛЮЦІЇ ГІДНОСТІ

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Мета статті — схарактеризувати розвиток сучасної святкової культури під впливом Революції гідності та дослідити її вплив на сучасні культурні процеси в Україні. Святкова культура об'єднує різні історико-культурні етапи життя українського суспільства. Водночас на сучасному етапі розвитку свята набувають нових виражальних і символічних форм, об'єднують громадян спільними ідеями, створюють той духовний стрижень, що нас єднає у свідому націю. Методологія дослідження передбачає використання загальнонаукового, історичного, порівняльного, аналітичного та аксіоматичного методів для системного аналізу процесу впливу Революції гідності на святкову українську культуру ХХІ ст. Наукова новизна полягає в тому, що в статті окреслено загальні тенденції розвитку українського святкового календаря після подій Революції гідності та в контексті російсько-української

війни, оскільки саме суспільні виклики сьогодення впливають на зміни нового святкового календаря українців. Висновки. Схарактеризовано розвиток сучасної святкової культури під впливом Революції гідності та досліджено її вплив на сучасні культурні процеси в Україні. Показано трансформацію традиційних і звичних для нас свят. На прикладах запровадження державних свят та пам'ятних дат продемонстровано взаємозв'язок головних подій суспільного життя зі святковим календарем країни. Доведено, що українська святкова культура, як феномен українського народу, здійснює активний вплив на розвиток та формування національної ідентичності як молодого покоління, так і дорослого населення країни. Отже, унікальність духовного багатства українського свята робить його неоціненним педагогічним доробком для виховання молоді, збереження національних традицій для прийдешніх поколінь.

Ключові слова: свято; святкова культура; Революція гідності; державне свято; пам'ятний день; календар державних свят

